

CESSDA Recommendations on Data Citation

Practical Recommendations for Key Stakeholders

Description

This document describes CESSDA recommendations for data citations. The core components of a data citation are presented, followed by specific and practical recommendations targeting different groups: 1) data repositories; 2) authors (i.e., researchers, students, journalists, etc.); 3) academic journals and publishers; 4) research performing organisations (RPOs); 5) high-level research policy and strategy development entities; and 6) ethics committees.

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Why Cite Data?

Research data are important outputs by themselves and should be addressable as an independent resource of research. Data citations promote seeing data as independent scientific products and give recognition to their producers. Furthermore, data citations foster research transparency and open science, aligning with good scholarly practices. Various scholars and institutions have discussed numerous reasons for the importance of data citations (see, e.g., Ball & Duke, 2015; Bornatici & Fedrigo, 2023; Dosso & Silvello, 2020; Finnish Social Science Data Archive, n.d.; FORCE11, 2014; ICPSR, 2018; Silvello, 2018; UK Data Service, 2023a). The objective of this section is not to conduct an exhaustive review but to highlight selected reasons that hold particular significance, encompassing the following aspects:

- **Accountability**
 - Data citations ensure that researchers and all actors in the data ecosystem receive proper recognition for their work following standard scientific practice.
 - Data citation ensures that data are addressable in the long term when it relates to a persistent identifier.
- **Reproducibility**
 - Reproducibility requires that the data and related contextual material are discoverable.
 - Data citations help to make data findable and accessible under certain conditions, which facilitates the reproducibility and verification of research and its results.
- **Policy compliance**
 - Data citations are often needed to fulfil the requirements of publishers, funders or research-producing organisations' data policies.
- **Reuse**
 - In the social sciences and humanities, research data have a scientific, cultural, or educational value that exceeds its original purpose of collection.
 - Providing independently addressable research data with associated metadata makes various reuse cases possible, including but not limited to:
 - Ensuring and demonstrating the reproducibility of a method used in a study
 - Exploring new research questions using existing data
 - Studying data citation and usage patterns

- Accessing the data specifically together with associated metadata using automated processes, such as metadata harvesting or AI applications
- Data citations are key elements of building knowledge graphs and connecting data, publications, authors, projects, and funding.

The Anatomy of a Data Citation: Core and Additional Components

A data citation is a reference to the data themselves and appears in-text or as a footnote whenever the data are either mentioned or directly referenced as a source, and the reference list should contain a corresponding entry (Bornatici & Fedrigo, 2023; FORCE11, 2014). The granularity of the reference depends on the usage. The data citation can identify the entire dataset or a subset.

To ensure proper identification and findability of the cited data, the data citation should comprise the following six core components (Bornatici & Fedrigo, 2023; Cousijn, H. et al. 2018; Finnish Committee for Research Data, 2018; IASSIST 2012; Jessop, 2021; Silvello, 2018; UK Data Service, 2023b):

- **Data author(s):** Name of each individual, research group, or organisational entity responsible for the creation of the data, sometimes referred to as data producer(s). This could also be the rights holder.
- **Title of the data:** Complete title of the data.
- **Year of publication:** Year the data were published or disseminated for the cited version of the data.
- **Version:** Version or edition number of the data. If not provided by the data publisher, the publication date or access date should be used instead.
- **Data publisher:** Organisational entity (e.g., data repository) responsible for making the data available by preserving and/or disseminating the data.
- **Persistent identifier:** Unique electronic identifier used to locate and access the data (such as a DOI).

While the above components should *always* be present in a data citation, additional components might add value or be requested by the publisher's/journal's guidelines or bibliographic styles (Bornatici & Fedrigo, 2023; Finnish Committee for Research Data, 2018):

- **Data number or accession number:** Unique numerical identifier for the data, provided by the data publisher. The data number is not a persistent identifier.

- **Resource type:** General resource type, often provided after the title in square brackets, e.g., [dataset], [data file and documentation]. This allows instant differentiation of data citations from other resource types.
- **Place of publication:** Physical location of the data publisher.

For instance, following APA 7th edition (APA Style, 2020), the formal data citation is formatted as follows:

Data author(s) (Publication year). *Data title* (Data number; Version) [Resource type].
Data publisher. Persistent identifier

Here are two examples of formal data citation following APA 7th edition guidelines:

Vanhanen, T. (2019). *Measures of Democracy 1810-2018* (FSD1289, Version 8.0) [Dataset]. Finnish Social Science Data Archive. <https://doi.org/10.60686/t-fsd1289>

ISSP Research Group (2023). *International Social Survey Programme: Environment IV – ISSP 2020* (ZA7650; Version 2.0.0) [Dataset]. GESIS. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14153>

Recommendations for Data Repositories

Recommendation 1 – Request data to be cited

Data repositories should request that data are cited whenever they are used or mentioned. Citing data is a sound scholarly practice. Enforcing the citation of data relies on contracts, licences, terms of use, or suggested best practices. Requesting data to be cited could also be stated in related documents included in the data package download folder, such as user terms and conditions, codebooks and data reports.

Recommendation 2 – Provide all six core data citation components

Data repositories should ensure that all data published are citable by providing at least the core components of a data citation, as listed above. Data repositories should check the quality of the metadata useful for the citation (e.g., explicit dataset title). Moreover, they are responsible for assigning a PID and providing the version (or publication date) for published datasets. Finally, for embargoed data, data repositories should provide a PID that allows data authors to cite the data in their research article. Reservation of a PID before the data are accessible should therefore be possible.

Recommendation 3 – Provide data versioning and access information

Data citations should include the version of a dataset (or a publication date) to ensure reproducibility. Therefore, data users may need to access specific versions of datasets, and information about changes and versions of data should be available. This could be provided through specific PIDs for each version of the dataset and/or a changelog, or versioning information text for concept PIDs. If a dataset or version of a dataset is no longer available, the PID assigned in the data citation should still lead to metadata about the dataset on the repository websites (e.g., a tombstone page). Moreover, data repositories should ensure access to metadata about all published versions of a dataset.

Recommendation 4 – Provide data citation suggestions including all six core components

User-friendly access to citation information for each dataset should be provided on the repository website. The data repositories should provide a data citation suggestion for each dataset. This suggestion should always include at least the six core components, and be visually noticeable. Providing this citation in multiple formats (e.g., APA, Chicago, and Harvard) is considered a good practice.

Recommendation 5 – Facilitate data citation for authors through export and download of metadata for reference management software

Data repositories should make it easy for users to automatically export and download data citation core components to reference management software. This will ensure that data can be cited in the same manner as other sources (such as journal articles, books, etc.) (Bornatici & Fedrigo, 2023). It is recommended that data repositories use formats that are compatible with commonly used reference management software (e.g., Endnote, Mendeley and Zotero), such as the RIS format (Research Information System Document). These files should include at least the six core components needed to build a data citation.

Recommendation 6 – Make citation information and other publication metadata accessible through generic structured metadata files

For the implementation of the FAIR principles, it is important to make sure that the six core components of a data citation are openly accessible together with other relevant information about the data publication as linked open metadata, thus providing a structured way of accessing a description of the data.

At least one generic metadata container should be provided with the data publication in a standardised and machine-actionable linked data format, for example, JSON-LD or RDF/XML. The actual metadata standards implemented may vary, but should at the very least cover

the basic needs of a data repository. An example of this is the DCAT standard (Albertoni et al., 2020). In specialised repositories, the schema used may depend on what relevant community standards are in use, for example, DDI-Lifecycle for the social sciences (DDI Alliance, 2024).

In addition to metadata standards established specifically for describing data, it is also advisable to provide metadata files or tags that use a generic metadata schema such as Schema.org (Payne & Verhey, 2022). This makes it more likely that infrastructures that are not specialised in research data will be able to reuse the six core components of a data citation and other information.

The metadata contents should reflect community standards and needs, while also providing generic information such as details on access methods, licensing and conditions for data reuse. Ideally, it should provide all structured information included in the data repository entry itself.

Recommendation 7 – Make data publications and relations to other entities machine-actionable through rich metadata and PIDs

In addition to the six core components of a data citation, the generic metadata containers should express relations between the data publication and other entities, using machine-actionable PIDs when possible. Examples of such PIDs and entities are ORCID for expressing relations to individuals, such as data authors and other contributors, ROR ID for expressing relations to organisations, such as research institutions, infrastructures or funders and DOI for expressing relations to publications and other digital objects. An example of expressing relations to publications would be including PIDs of publications citing the data as relations of a specific “cited by” type in the metadata. Such relations may also be enhanced over time by external metadata contributors.

Data may be published with different hierarchical relations and varying granularity. Whenever possible, this should be expressed with PIDs and machine-actionable metadata. For example, a DOI could be provided pointing to the conceptual level of a data publication, with other DOIs pointing to specific versions or subsets of the data publication. In such cases, the latter type of PID would most often be the appropriate choice for inclusion in a data citation.

Recommendation 8 – Raise awareness about data citation

Data repositories should inform data users on data citation best practices, for example through their general information materials or accompanying dataset documentation. Data repositories should also target data producers specifically and encourage them to cite their data and report the shared datasets alongside traditional research outputs. Similarly, data repositories should suggest to research institutions to include data collection and sharing, as

well as data citations, in their research assessment process. In addition to creating specific documentation and teaching materials, seminars and presentations could be conducted to inform different stakeholders like researchers, students, institutions, funders, and journals on best practices. Data repositories could thus emphasise the benefits of correct data citation, such as aligning with open data principles and fostering better research practices. Recognising data authors for sharing data gives them more incentives to share their data, which ultimately increases repository content.

Recommendations for Authors¹

Recommendation 1 – Cite the data themselves

The citation should refer to the data specifically. Acknowledgements and data availability statements, as well as references to methodological reports or data articles, do not qualify as data citations. All data used or mentioned in a publication must be cited both in the text, often in a short version (e.g., author-date), and in the reference list in a full version.

Recommendation 2 – Include all six core components for data citation in the reference list

While citing the data, make sure that all the core components are included in the citation. These are the minimal components. The components are provided by dedicated data repositories where the data are published openly or with restricted access.

Arrange the citation core components and add additional components and information based on the requirements of the bibliographic style, journal/publisher guidelines, or data repository demands. While most reference styles accommodate authors, title, publication year, publisher, and the inclusion of a URL, certain components specific to data citations – such as the version (a core component) or resource type (an additional component) – may not be directly supported. In such cases, these details can be incorporated into the title field.

Data repositories usually provide a suggestion for the data citation, or even an automatic download of the core components that could be uploaded in a reference management software (e.g., Zotero, EndNote, Mendeley). Verify that the upload includes all six core components of the data citation. You might also want to include information related to additional components.

¹ This section draws heavily from Bornatici and Fedrigo (2023).

For embargoed data deposited in a repository, the deposit year and date can be used instead of the published year and version, respectively. Alternatively, “Forthcoming” can be mentioned instead of the published year. The data repository might be able to communicate the persistent identifier.

Recommendation 3 – Cite specifically primary and secondary data, as well as replication materials

Authors should cite the data they analyse, which can be data collected by themselves (primary data) or data collected by other researchers for another research purpose (secondary data).

In addition, authors might also be requested to share their replication materials, that is material for reproducibility purposes which may contain data, code, software, and other project files. In this case, both the (primary or secondary) data and the replication materials should be cited accurately and, if possible, separately. Indeed, in the interest of transparency and accountability, the authors using secondary data must cite the secondary data themselves in their publication. Citing only the replication materials that are authored by themselves is not sufficient in this case.

For authors using their own data (primary data), both the data and the replication materials have the same authors, as opposed to when reusing secondary data. However, these two research outputs contain different information and have different purposes. If the replication materials often include only the subset of data used in the analyses (e.g., some observations, variables, or other components), there is generally more data collected within the research project that could be shared in a data repository. Therefore, the data shared in the replication materials is mainly meant to verify and reproduce the results, while the ‘complete’ data could be reused in the future to answer new research questions. Consequently, it is recommended to publish and share data that are as complete data as possible in order to enable further reuse.

Recommendations for Journals and Publishers

Recommendation 1 – Allow data citations in the standard list of references

Journals should allow citations of data or replication materials (such as software or project files) to be listed together with other references in the standard reference list of an article.

Journals should not limit authors to only mentioning or citing the data in the Data Availability Statement (DAS), or in the acknowledgement section. DAS sections are useful to clarify how

data might be accessed or requested. However, they do not mitigate the need for a full data citation in the reference list. The DAS section is rarely usable as a machine-readable metadata source, and will often be ignored by metadata indexing.

Reference lists are an important metadata source for citation indexing, metrics and relational mapping. Excluding cited data from reference lists limits the findability, reach and possible reuse of a data publication, limits machine readability, and creates fewer incentives for authors to publish FAIR data.

Recommendation 2 – Require authors to cite data specifically

Journals should require authors to cite any data, whether they are simply mentioned in the manuscript or underlying their results. This also includes complete datasets or partial datasets necessary for replication purposes, for instance. They should instruct authors to cite actual data publications when available, and not only publications relating to the data (such as methodological reports, data articles, etc.). The data must be cited specifically in the text and in the reference list, regardless if it is primary material (developed by the article's authors) or secondary material (developed by other researchers). As a specific type of primary material, replication materials such as code, software, or project files should also be cited specifically in relevant sections of the text and in the reference list.

Recommendation 3 – Include all six core components in data citations and provide citation examples

Journals should choose reference styles with rules that do not prevent the inclusion of all six core components of a data citation in the reference list. Moreover, journals should provide clear examples of well-formed data citations including all core components in their submission guidelines for authors.

While most reference styles accommodate authors, title, publication year, publisher, and the inclusion of a URL, certain components specific to data citations – such as the version (a core component) or resource type (an additional component) – may not be directly supported. In such cases, these details can be incorporated into the title field.

Recommendation 4 – Encourage authors to publish data and replication materials as independent publications

Journals should encourage authors to publish related data and replication materials as independent publications in suitable repositories. Both open and restricted data publications should follow the FAIR data principles. Merely stating in the article that data are available upon request does not qualify as an independent data publication.

Journals should not consider data or replication materials to be mere supplements or appendices to an article. Moreover, they should not encourage authors to upload supplement file attachments to journal publishing platforms as an alternative to independent publishing

in a data repository or code repository. Data hidden away in supplement file attachments will have limited visibility for indexing and will rarely fulfil the FAIR data principles. It should however be noted that some publisher infrastructures do provide suitable data repositories for making independent data publications.

If data and replication materials are both available, journals should suggest that authors publish them as separate publications. If it is not possible to publish data with open access, they should encourage authors to make formal and independent publications of data with restricted access. Both the replication materials and the data should, if possible, refer to each other using full citations as well as PIDs. This is preferable to a single publication containing both data and replication materials. Separate publications will allow better addressability in citations and encourage a modular and reusable approach to replication packaging. In some cases, a modular approach will allow sharing of replication materials as an independent publication with open access, while access to the data or subset of data themselves may be restricted. However, in certain cases packaging and publishing both data and replication materials as a single publication might be a better option because of requirements in certain workflows or standards.

Recommendation 5 - Encourage authors to provide PIDs for published data and replication materials

Journals should also encourage authors to provide persistent identifiers (PIDs) for published data and replication materials when submitting content. This enables stable and unambiguous references to such publications, which is also why a PID is one of the six core components of a data citation. Authors may use dedicated repository services that provide PIDs or register them using other means, such as through specific research infrastructures or automated workflows providing PID assignments. PIDs should be provided for open-access data publications as well as for restricted data publications where only metadata may be publicly available. Generic sample numbers and other identifiers that are not machine-actionable do not qualify as PIDs.

Recommendation 6 - Allow sufficient time for quality assurance and data curation

Journals and authors should be aware that formal data publications in trusted data repositories often need to pass through review and quality assurance. They should inform authors that they should expect a curation process before the data publication is made publicly available. Journals should account for this curation process, which may require several amendments before being approved, similar to the peer review process of a journal manuscript. To streamline publication timelines, journals should encourage researchers to deposit their data and replication materials before or during the article review process (e.g., after the first peer review), and if needed make the data and replication materials accessible

only to the reviewers during the article review process. This ensures that by the time the article is ready for publication, the data and the final version of the replication materials are also ready to be published or have already been published.

Recommendations for Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)

Recommendation 1 - Encourage data citation practices

RPOs should encourage authors to cite data specifically in the same manner as detailed in the Specific Recommendations for Authors.

Guidelines and best practices disseminated by the RPO should recommend citing data specifically, providing at least the six core components of a data citation. Examples of this could be requirements or recommendations in open science policies, web content guidelines, course materials and instructions for students, PhD handbooks or formal requirements for theses and report series, etc.

Recommendation 2 - Encourage authors to report data publications when reporting their research outputs

RPOs should encourage data authors to submit information on data publications when actively reporting their research outputs to institutional repositories, bibliographic metadata catalogues, library catalogues, publication lists on faculty profile pages, and similar functions or infrastructures.

Authors should be encouraged to provide the six core components of a data citation as a minimum amount of metadata when reporting a data publication.

Recommendation 3 - Include data publication metadata in institutional repositories, publication lists and similar indexing services

RPOs should treat data publications as a valid research output and enable indexing of such publications in institutional repositories, bibliographic metadata catalogues, library catalogues and similar services. They should include at least the six core components of a data citation in the metadata for data publications. If possible, data publications should be distinguishable in entries and metadata by being treated as a unique resource type, such as "Dataset".

RPOs should, if possible, make efforts to find and index past data publications using available metadata sources, especially if data publications have not been included in active research output reporting in the past.

RPOs should make sure that indexed data publications are reported together with other institutional research outputs to national research publication indexes, national CRIS or grant tracking systems, national library catalogues, and similar infrastructures if relevant. The reported metadata for a data publication should include at least the six core components of a data citation.

If possible, information about additional contributors and organisations, related publications, research project identifiers, funder identifiers and grant IDs should also be included in the reported data publication metadata, using machine-actionable PIDs when feasible. This will enable a large-scale overview and assessment of research outputs.

Recommendation 4 - Include and leverage the added value of metadata describing data publications in DMP tools, research information systems and similar administrative infrastructures

Research project management and administration conducted by RPOs may make use of project indexing support systems, such as current research information systems (CRIS), also known as Research Information Management Systems (RIMS). RPOs may also use other tools for creating reusable project-related structured metadata and documentation, such as tools for creating data management plans. When possible, RPOs should facilitate the production and inclusion of data publication metadata, encourage citing data and aid data publication flows using such support systems.

Examples of this could be using existing project metadata to automatically create pre-populated metadata entries for data publications to be completed at a later date, requesting details about FAIR data publication planning at an early stage, and allowing metadata input of at least the six core components of a data citation when prompting for information about planned or published new data publications. Secondary data used in the project should likewise be included in the metadata using at least the six core components.

By including data publication metadata in tools and support systems at an early stage, project members will be encouraged to relate to and actively and systematically cite existing data as well as new data throughout the project. This may also streamline the data publishing process and aid in decision-making. At the same time, requirements for making data publications FAIR will be highlighted and early planning will be promoted.

Support systems may also aid data publication workflows by providing access to a selection of project metadata in advance to be used by external infrastructures, such as data repositories in preparation of publication entries, or metadata aggregators enabling scientific knowledge graphs.

Recommendation 5 - Take data publications into account when performing institutional bibliometric analysis or creating output summaries

RPOs often use bibliometric analysis or other output summaries as a part of the process of mapping research outputs of institutions, departments or research groups. Whenever possible, they should consider data publications as a valid research output and take them into account when analysing or summarising outputs.

Data publications should be included in this process to provide a more complete basis for research assessment and reporting. Taking data publications into account is also likely to encourage data producers and authors to publish formal data publications as well as to cite data when relevant. RPOs are key stakeholders for creating and maintaining a sustainable data citation culture.

Recommendations for High-Level Research Policy and Strategy Development Entities²

Recommendation 1 – Require data to be cited

Research policy-making organisations and agencies should include a clear statement in their binding policy documents and recommendations requiring that research data be cited whenever they are used and mentioned. Publishing data (whether openly or under restricted access) and citing data should be considered essential for making research results replicable and the research process transparent. Organisations adhering to these policies should incorporate this requirement into their policies such as national open science policies, data policies, or PID policies. The policies should also suggest ways to monitor compliance and address instances of non-compliance.

Recommendation 2 – Include all six core components in the guiding policies

Through their policies, research policy-making organisations and agencies should stress that proper data citation – to fulfil the goals associated with citing data – requires at least the

² These high-level entities provide guiding recommendations and binding policies within Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), and regional, national, and cross-national bodies.

use of all the six core components. It should be noted that depositing data in a repository capable of providing the citation elements is a default expectation.

Recommendation 3 – Make the benefits of proper data citation clear in the policies

Scholarly citation requires that research data are referred to with the same rigour as other research outputs. In particular, policies that guide the openness, transparency, and reproducibility of research should emphasise that referring to research data not only promotes these goals but, in addition, makes it possible to increase the impact of science by referring to the data directly and by building various automated ways to enrich and create knowledge graphs when persistent identifiers are in place as required by the core components. Furthermore, policies should highlight that data citation practices are recognised as a key element of open and FAIR science and are increasingly incorporated into researcher evaluations and funding assessments.

Recommendation 4 - Require active reporting of data publication outputs through national or cross-national generic or field-specific infrastructures

Limited availability of metadata describing data publications creates obstacles for large-scale interlinking, monitoring and assessment of research outputs. When creating policies concerning research output reporting, policy makers should require RPOs to regularly report data publication metadata to relevant infrastructures such as research publication indexes, CRIS systems, grant tracking systems or library catalogues on a national or cross-national level. These infrastructures may be generic or cater to a specific research field.

Reported metadata should include at least the six core components of a data citation. If possible, it should also include information about additional contributors and organisations, related publications, research project identifiers, funder identifiers and grant IDs, using machine-actionable PIDs when feasible. Extensive availability of unambiguous and machine-readable metadata interlinking data publications with other entities will enable the implementation of scientific knowledge graphs as well as discovery and citation tools with widespread coverage.

Recommendations for Ethics Committees³

Recommendation 1 - All research should follow good citation practice

Ethics committees emphasise that recognising the work of others is a research ethical value and a prerequisite for the scientific community to work collegially, responsibly and in a self-correcting manner. Research data should be used ethically by mentioning the source. Therefore, proper citation is necessary whenever conclusions, methods, ideas, and actual research material drawn from data are quoted or used or mentioned in any research output, including a dataset. Negligence can be considered a violation of research ethics and plagiarism or fraud (National Committee for Research Ethics in the Social Sciences and the Humanities, 2021).

All citations must be made in a manner that complies with any licences or terms of use set by the data authors or a body acting on their behalf, such as a repository. The same should apply to citing copyrighted, openly licensed or public domain material.

Recommendation 2 – Even restricted data should be citable

Ethics committees should in their guidance and decisions emphasise the importance of giving proper credit to the data sources used in research, especially if these data were collected from human participants. Citing data, even in the case when actual data cannot be made available due to ethical issues or access is in other ways restricted due to privacy concerns, should be underlined.

Recommendation 3 - Address data citation in data management plans

Ethics committees should encourage researchers to address data citation practices in their data management plans submitted for ethical review. Proper citation is an essential aspect of research integrity and transparency. Addressing this in DMPs allows researchers to demonstrate their commitment to best data citation practices.

In addition, to raise awareness, ethics review forms should include an informative section about data sharing, data citation, and best practices.

³ Ethics committees act on different levels and serve different purposes. They provide ethical review of research projects and activities, and may be institutional review boards (IRBs), other institutional or national ethics boards, journal ethics committees or other similar entities.

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